

PREVENTION OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES**Andijan State Medical Institute****Endosurgery, endourology and****senior teacher of the department of dentistry****Abdurakhmonova Mukhayokhan Abdurakhimovna**

Abstract: The article presents examples of the use of various methods of temporary teeth splinting. The main task of the temporary bite of teeth with damage to the periodontal tissue is to lower and unite the teeth with subsequent fixation of the weakened periodontal tissue in the presence of a damaged articulation or formed traumatic knots. Temporary structures and various splint devices fix mobile teeth and optimally distribute the chewing load to mobile teeth, teeth with sufficiently well-preserved periodontium, and teeth that do not participate in all chewing movements.

Key words: Stomatology, orthopedic dentistry, tooth splint, tooth mobility, periodontal disease, temporary splinting.

The basis of the instructions for cutting teeth is the assessment of their mobility and the condition of the periodontal tissue, which is determined on the basis of clinical and X-ray examination after therapeutic and surgical treatment methods. In case of loss of bone tissue half the length of the tooth root, it is necessary to perform horizontal splinting, which consists of the use of sagittal and transverse splinting methods. When diagnosing bone loss up to % of the root length and II-III tooth mobility, it is necessary to use rigid splints in three planes (vertical, sagittal and transverse). The degree of mobility of the teeth, the state and severity of periodontal tissue inflammation lies in the choice of the type of stabilization - frontal (front part); - sagittal (lateral part of the dental arch); - fronto-sagittal; parasagittal; - stabilization of the arc. Splinting of mobile teeth with preserved teeth with weakened periodontium involves combining them into a single block, planning the optimal design of the splint to maximize the combination of a large number of teeth with weakened and preserved periodontium. In the event of a violation of the integrity of the dental cavity, splinting of mobile teeth should be carried out simultaneously with the restoration of defects in the tooth structure. At the same time, it is necessary to distinguish between a group of gear teeth and a prosthetic structure, which in most cases, in one way or another, loads the splined teeth through the support system on the clamping and locking fasteners of the clamp. prostheses. When choosing such designs of devices, it is necessary to optimally

distribute the functions of support and retention with minimal damage and overloading of the remaining 29 teeth.

Orthopedic structures used in the complex treatment of a patient with periodontal tissue diseases are represented by temporary and permanent splints and prosthetic structures. Temporary splints are used in all medical, therapeutic and surgical treatments to stabilize moving or migrating teeth, as well as in the production of permanent abutments or the production of a permanent prosthetic structure. With slightly bent teeth or their displacement, temporary splints should be used to transfer and correct the results of orthodontic treatment. Temporary splints provide optimal distribution of chewing pressure between the periodontium of affected and intact teeth, give rest to affected tissues, improve their trophism, remove the inflammatory component in periodontal tissues. Temporary splints are widely used in advanced stages of focal and general periodontitis. Their use makes it possible to evenly redistribute the mechanical energy of chewing pressure between the periodontium of the teeth included in the block, which creates rest for the affected tissues, which improves the blood supply of the periodontal tissues and reduces the inflammatory process. will bring. The absolute indication for the production of a temporary splint is gingivotomy and gingivectomy. The use of modern composite materials has significantly expanded the indications for the use of temporary splints that optimally fix removable teeth directly on the seat in accordance with aesthetic and hygienic requirements. With the loss of front teeth, individual teeth can be replaced using composites.

Depending on the chemical composition, two types of materials are used for splinting mobile teeth: GlasSpan and FiberSplint (Switzerland) based on an inorganic matrix; based on an organic matrix made of polyethylene Ribbond (USA) and Connect (USA). These materials are based on a matrix of the best fibers of polyethylene or microfiber quartz impregnated with a composite, which allows them to be firmly fixed to the crown of the teeth, and then composite materials are added to the matrix for better mechanical properties. fasten the mobile teeth, make one tire block. Recently, intraoral scanning has been widely implemented in dentistry. This method allows you to accurately obtain a digital model of the relief of objects of the oral cavity. After taking an optical impression, various protective mouth guards, temporary splints and splints are made in CAD/CAM systems. An important feature of CAD/CAM systems available in the modern market is their versatility in terms of the choice of construction materials. The technological capabilities of the equipment include not only computer modeling of the prosthetic project, but also the direct execution of the finished product, which, in particular, allows orthopedic dentistry to provide various temporary splints taking into account individual

anatomical and individual anatomical characteristics. provides the necessary resources for creation. physiological features of the facial skull structure. Sufficiently strong 30 splinting structures can be made using braided titanium or stainless wire. Before splinting, all supra- and subgingival deposits should be carefully removed.

Using a copy marker, the interfering contact points are aligned and then removed during sagittal and transverse physiological movements within the occlusal field. After drilling the composite and final polymerization using polishers, the final surface treatment of the tire structure is carried out, the final alignment of the occlusal contacts is carried out with forced release of the gingival interdental papillae. Similar designs of manufactured tires can last 3-5 years. The period of use of such a splint is determined by the existing mobility of the teeth, oral hygiene and therapeutic treatment of periodontal tissue diseases. It is very important to take into account the characteristics of the materials from which the future structures will be made during the work process. Intolerance to dental materials can occur for various reasons: galvanism, allergic reactions to dental materials, toxic damage to the mucous membrane, etc., so it is necessary to strictly control the quality of the materials used (do not allow the use of fake products) and in addition, if necessary, joint analysis of materials by a dentist and an immunological laboratory.

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